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NEW MOLECULAR MARKERS FOR EM AND EG S.L.: FROM RAPID DIAGNOSTICS TO SOURCE ATTRIBUTION

1. New mitochondrial markers (Subtask 1, UT)

Designing diagnostic tools for *Echinococcus* species requires detailed knowledge of range-wide genetic variation. Mitochondrial genome has been a genetic marker of choice for diagnostics, primarily due to its high copy number that facilitates analysis of *Echinococcus* samples even for partially degraded samples. To develop species and genotype specific diagnostic assays, we sequenced mitochondrial genomes using a worldwide scale panel of different *E. granulosus* s.l. (Eg sl) and *E. multilocularis* (Em) species and genotypes. For genotypes Eg ss genotypes G1 and G3 we sequenced near-complete mitogenomes (11,682 bp), leaving out repetitive non-coding sequences in the mitogenome (Kinkar et al. 2019) that are difficult to sequence. For other species and genotypes we sequenced complete genomes. During the working process, it became clear that the genetic variation of Eg sl is significantly higher compared to Em and requires more input from Eg sl, especially of genotype G1 that had very high genetic variability. Therefore, we changed the original strategy and included more Eg sl samples (N=392; from 25 countries) into the analysis, compared to Em (N=108; from 12 countries), keeping the total number of 500 samples as originally planned. The mitogenome variation of Eg ss, especially of G1, is very high. The overall haplotype diversity (Hd) index for genotype G1 was (Hd = 0.992) and the nucleotide diversity was 0.00129. The huge variation of genotype G1 is illustrated in Figure 1. Other species and genotypes had significantly lower variation. Based on the genetic variability data of Eg sl and Em, we developed Toehold Exchange Probes for a reliable and rapid identification of all species and genotypes of Eg sl and Em. Testing these probes is in progress.

Figure 1. Worldwide phylogenetic network of *E. granulosus* s.s. (G1) samples based on near-complete mitogenome sequences. Colours represent distinct haplogroups.

2. New microsatellite markers (Subtask 2, Anses)

2.1.1. Epidemiological context

Echinococcus granulosus sensu stricto (ss) is the dominant species (88% of infections identified at species level) responsible of human cases of cystic echinococcosis (CE) in the world (Alvarez-Rojas et al. 2014). This parasite species is widespread globally and notably in southern Europe in countries around the Mediterranean basin. The numerous data previously obtained in different geographical regions about genetic diversity were from short sequences of several mitochondrial genes resulting to a low phylogenetic resolution and not directly comparable. The use of near-complete mitogenome sequences (11,443 bp) has result to obtain great advances in the difference between G1 and G3 genotypes and also in the genetic diversity information of samples from different areas in the world (Kinkar et al. 2017, 2018). Nevertheless this large Sanger sequencing approach is fastidious, time-consuming and quite expensive preventing its common use for epidemiological studies. In this context, another approach based on microsatellite genotyping will be welcome due to its low cost and quickness of use with a similar potential to describe genetic diversity. The recent sequencing of the nuclear genome opens the possibility to use bioinformatic tools to search for microsatellite sequences.

2.2. Material and methods

2.2.1. Collection of samples

Eg ss samples were collected from different localizations in southern Europe (Greece and Italy) and from northern Africa (Tunisia, Algeria, Morocco) in order to have a preliminary overview of the genetic diversity around the Mediterranean basin. When some samples were used to a first selection of the microsatellites, all the 91 others were added to validate the final panel.

2.2.2. Research of microsatellites targets

A systematic research for single-locus microsatellites was performed on the nuclear genome of *Eg* ss (v2 03232012, Sanger Institute) using the Tandem Repeats Finder software. Among proposed repeated patterns, only microsatellites showing at least ten repeated units and showing unit length comprised between 3 and 10 were selected. For the best candidates, PCR primer pairs were designed in order to test the amplification and observed their polymorphism with some test samples (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Examples of the electrophoretic profiles obtained for one *Eg* ss sample for three of the selected loci.

2.2.3. Validation of a microsatellites panel

The microsatellites selected have to be validated regarding the polymorphism of each target with the larger panel of samples from the three countries. The package PoppR in R was used to validate the number of required microsatellites needed and perform the selection of the panel according to the genetic diversity observed for each target and their ability to be successfully amplified.

2.3. Results and discussion

The screening of the *Eg ss* genome resulted in the identification of 15 new interesting microsatellites targets. After amplification tests and rapid observation of the polymorphism, six targets were selected to establish a panel. The EgSca6 microsatellite previously used in MEME (M'Rad et al., 2020) was added to those six selected. A plateau has been reached with the genotype accumulation analyses using the seven loci selected confirming a highly discrimination power between unique individuals (Figure 3). A total of 90 multilocus genotypes (MLG) were identified among the 91 samples using the 7 microsatellites targets.

Figure 3: Number of genotypes as a function of the number of loci combined to discriminate genotypes of *Egss* samples.

The panel is composed of 7 microsatellites, 5 targets with trinucleotide motifs and 2 with tetranucleotide motifs. A very high discriminatory power was obtained using the validation panel of 91 samples with 10 to 48 alleles described according to the different targets with very high diversity index (Simpson or Nei's) and with very evenly distributed alleles (Table 1).

Table 1: Description of the number of alleles, genetic diversity index and evenness observed for the 91 samples tested with the seven microsatellites targets of the panel.

locus	Number of alleles	Simpson index (1-D)	Hexp (Nei's index)	Evenness
Sca1_TTG	32.00	0.94	0.95	0.79
Sca7_GGAT	46.00	0.97	0.97	0.80
Sca3_ATCC	10.00	0.63	0.63	0.52
Sca6_CAT	29.00	0.94	0.95	0.77
Sca2_GTT	18.00	0.90	0.90	0.78
Sca6_TGG	48.00	0.96	0.97	0.74
Sca6_GAA	14.00	0.80	0.80	0.63
mean	28.14	0.88	0.88	0.72

Using the five populations, a preliminary population study can be realized. A high genetic diversity was observed in the five populations regarding the number of multilocus genotypes and both Simpson and Nei's Index (Hexp) (Table 2). The index of association obtained suggests that populations recombine at low rates, but that reproduction is mainly clonal.

Table 2: Population statistics obtained for each of the five populations of Eg ss samples analysed by the panel of microsatellites. Number of expected MLG was calculated at the smallest sample size (10) based on rarefaction.

Population	Number of samples	Number of MLG	Number of expected MLG	Standard error based on eMLG	Simpson's Index	Evenness	Hexp	Index of association	Standardized index of association
Morocco	10	10	10.00	0.00e+00	0.9	1.000	0.819	0.106	0.0184
Algeria	22	22	10.00	0.00e+00	0.955	1.000	0.792	0.639	0.1093
Tunisia	11	11	10.00	0.00e+00	0.909	1.000	0.874	1.879	0.3496
Italy	17	17	10.00	2.31e-07	0.941	1.000	0.855	1.003	0.1867
Greece	31	30	9.90	2.96e-01	0.966	0.982	0.862	1.798	0.3162
Total	91	90	9.99	1.04e-01	0.989	0.993	0.881	0.632	0.1096

There is no common multilocus genotypes between countries excepting one shared by two samples from Greece. Nevertheless, the visualization of the genetic distance calculated using Bruvo's distance allows to distinguish one cluster composed by 21 samples from Greece, another one with 5 samples from Algeria but also one from Italy and Greece, a third one with five samples from Greece one from Italy when the others samples are grouped in different clusters with samples from different origins (Figure 4). The presence of clusters grouping samples from the different Mediterranean countries was also observed using near-complete mitochondrial genome sequencing confirming the important intermingling linked to the domestication and exchange of animals (Kinkar et al. 2018).

Figure 4: Minimum spanning network of the five Mediterranean populations of Eg ss using Bruvo's distance calculated from data of the panel of the seven microsatellites selected.

The panel composed of the seven microsatellites targets obtained is able to describe a very high genetic diversity and confirms to be a relevant alternative to classical Sanger sequencing of whole or near-complete mitogenome in order to perform phylogenetic studies but also source attribution.

3. NGS-based method (Subtask 3, UT)

Mitogenome data can pose a means to track the source of infection. Human infections can nowadays (due to extensive travelling) occur abroad and testing the origin of infection requires an effective method for testing. The very high variability of *E. granulosus* s.s. (Eg ss) at the mitogenome level, especially of genotype G1 that is the most prevalent genotype among humans, provides a possibility to perform source attribution analysis. During this project a method was developed that enables to sequence 96 mitogenomes in a single sequencing run, using short-read next generation sequencing (SR-NGS). Based on extensive knowledge of genetic variability of the genus *Echinococcus*, obtained from WP3-T1-ST2, we developed primers that enable PCR-amplification of the entire mitogenome in a single PCR. However, as the PCR amplification of the entire mitochondrial genome requires high-quality DNA, but in reality the DNA quality of parasite samples varies and often important samples are of low quality, we also developed primers that allow PCR amplification of the whole mitogenome in four fragments. The latter approach was proven to be significantly more efficient compared to the amplification of mitochondrial genome in one PCR, especially for Eg ss that contain repetitive non-coding sequences in the mitogenome (Kinkar et al. 2019). The four-primer approach was used to analyse 96 samples in a single SR-NGS run, which allows easy and cost-effective generation of highly accurate mitogenome sequences (the principal workflow is presented in Figure 5).

Figure 5: A schematic representation of the workflow for sequencing *Echinococcus* mitogenomes in four overlapping fragments, using short-read next generation sequencing.

4. References

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